

Experimental Investigation of Oxyfuel Combustion of Hydrogen-Containing Fuel Gases in Industrial Glass Burners

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The use of green hydrogen as a substitute for natural gas offers considerable potential for reducing climate-relevant emissions such as CO₂ in the glass manufacturing industry. Since the complete substitution of thermal heating by electrical or other alternative concepts is currently only feasible to a limited extent and natural gas continues to be the dominant energy source, this work focuses on the investigation of hydrogen-based fuel gases. The combustion of hydrogen with air at the high temperatures required for glass processes is associated with increased nitrogen oxide emissions, which is why the use of oxygen supported combustion (oxyfuel) is considered a promising alternative and also enables higher efficiency.

Experimental Setup

- The investigated burner consists of two parts: the mixture periphery and four interchangeable burner heads with different geometries
- Every nozzle has a circular hole with a diameter of 1.13 mm and a ring gap with inner and outer diameter of 1.87 mm and 3.11 mm respectively
- Original mounting position: fuel flow is through ring gap and oxygen flow through circular hole
Swapped mounting position: oxygen flow is through ring gap and fuel flow through circular hole (BH1 and BH2 are also investigated in this position)
- The current investigation evaluates the operating ranges of the burner and all four burner heads for hydrogen oxygen as well as natural gas oxygen mixtures for non-premixed flames
- Supply line/ MFC limitations: $Q_{O_2,max}$: 10 m³/h; $P_{therm,NG,max}$: 50 kW; $P_{therm,H_2,max}$: 45 kW

Figure 1: Experimental Setup with a) mixture periphery and interchangeable burner heads, b) original nozzle flow c) BH1: 9 nozzles, d) BH2: 21 nozzles, e) BH3: 22 nozzles, f) BH4: 45 nozzles

Results and Discussion

Figure 2: Natural gas oxygen flames at 5 kW for a) $\phi = 2$, b) $\phi = 1$, and c) $\phi = 0.83$. Left original mounting position, right swapped mounting position.

- Figure 2 shows that the mounting position has a large influence on the flame structure
- Lift off already takes place for the flame in Figure 2 c) on the left while the one on the right side is stable

Table 1: Measurement ranges for each burner head for thermal power and equivalence ratio

Burner Head	No. 1	No. 2 – 4
Lowest Thermal Power	1	2.5
Equivalence ratio (ϕ)	0.2 – 2	0.2 – 2

- Supply line limitations encountered:

- $P_{therm,H_2,max}$ with BH4 (MFC)
- $Q_{O_2,max}$ for the burner heads 1 and 2 mounted in swapped direction (MFC)
- The maximum thermal power for the swapped mounted heads is limited due to the supply line pressure

- When the gas exit velocities are slow, e.g. at different combinations of low thermal power and high equivalence ratios, there is no operation possible due to glowing of nozzles
- Glowing mainly happens with H₂ as can be seen in all operating ranges in Figure 4 and less often with NG
- Operation at higher thermal power and lower equivalence ratio is mainly not possible due to flame lift off or the supply line limitations for the swapped mounting position
- Lift off does not occur if the burner heads are mounted in the swapped position
- Operating ranges for burner heads 1 and 2 are larger if they are mounted in swapped position
- If the fuel gas exits the nozzle through the inner circular hole it is more likely to be burnt because it is surrounded by a high temperature gas as can be seen on the right in Figure 3

Figure 3: Natural gas oxygen flame at 4 kW and $\phi = 1$ for, left, original mounting position and right, swapped mounting position

- If the fuel exits the nozzle through the ring gap it is not surrounded by a hot gas as can be seen on the left in Figure 3 and thus less likely to be burnt
- With decreasing equivalence ratio the exit velocity of oxygen increases and leads to lift off in the original mounting position

Figure 4: Operating ranges for oxy-fuel combustion of natural gas and hydrogen using: a) Head 1, b) Head 2, c) Head 3, d) Head 4, e) Head 1 swapped, and f) Head 2 swapped. Coloured graphs are the lowest possible equivalence ratios for each fuel

Conclusion

- Operating ranges for the given burner are determined; BH mounted in the swapped position offer a wider operating range than mounted in the original position
- Natural gas can be used for low thermal power to prevent glowing of the nozzles especially with BH1 in either mounting position
- Mounted in the original position, hydrogen offers an up to 2.5 times larger operating range (BH2) in terms of thermal power
- Mounted in the swapped position, natural gas and hydrogen show similar operating ranges for each investigated burner head
- BH2 in swapped mounting position has the best overall performance and is the most versatile out of the investigated one

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